
Solid State Study for Barbituric Acid and Uracil Thorium Complexes

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Abstract Syntheses of barbituric acid and uracil Th complexes have been reported. Elemental analysis of the prepared metal complexes, structural investigation of the complexes to know their geometries and mode of bonding based on: Infrared, electronic spectra, dielectric measurements and magnetic susceptibility were studied. The thermal behavior of Th(BA)₂ complex has been studied applying differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Thermodynamic parameters, decompositions and thermal stabilities are calculated and explained. Some theoretical studies were carried out to obtain the charges, bond lengths, bond angles, and dihedral angles of the studied ligands, where the chemical potential, electronegativity, hardness and softness are determined, using hyperchem program. Molecular modeling of the ligands was performed using PC computer to give extra spot lights on the bonding properties of these compounds.

Keywords Barbituric acid and uracil Th complexes, Thermal behavior, DSC, Dielectric measurements, Molecular Modeling

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Introduction

Many techniques were recorded in bioinformatics for DNA microarray data. These are mainly based on fold-change analysis, clustering, classification, genetic network analysis, and simulation [1].

The pyrimidines and purines are of great importance [2], where in our laboratory, numerous papers have been published from the structural and coordination chemistry views [3-20].

The pyrimidine nucleus is embedded in a large number of alkaloids, drugs, antibiotics, agrochemicals, and antimicrobial agents. Many fused pyrimidines such as purines and pteridines are biologically active by themselves, or are essential components of very important naturally occurring substances (*i.e.*, nucleic acids).

The manifestation of the purine system in natural products has been reviewed [21]. Fluorouracil or the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) drug zidovudine compounds are of biological interest in chemotherapy. Ultrashort-acting barbiturates such as thiopental sodium (Pentothal) [22] are often used as general anesthetics, whereas methylphenobarbital [23] is used as antiepilepticum. Some diaminopyrimidines, such as pyrimethamine or trimethoprim are powerful antimalaria drugs used in combination with sulfonamides, is also a potent antibacteriostaticum, whereas minoxidil [24] is used as antihypertensive. Sulfadiazine is one of the chemotherapeutics containing a pyrimidine moiety.

The aim of the present article is related to study the mode of bonding, electronic absorption, magnetic properties, thermal analysis (DSC), dielectric constant, electrical conductivity and molecular modeling of barbituric acid, uracil and their Th complexes.

Experimental

The ligands used are

Barbituric acid (BA)

Uracil (U)

Synthesis of metal complexes in the solid state

These were prepared by mixing metal salt solutions with ligand solutions; hence they were refluxed, filtered and dried for the separated products.

The complexes were digested by aqua-regia several times to complete decomposition for the organic ligand compounds. The metal was determined by atomic absorption techniques and complexometric titrations by using published procedures. The analyzed complex is given in Table (1).

Table 1: C, H, N, M elemental analysis for Th(BA)₂ complex

Complex	Colour	Formula	Calculated/(Found) %			
			C	H	N	M
Th(BA) ₂	yellow	C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₆ O ₉ Th	23.54 (23.72)	1.32 (1.55)	13.73 (14.00)	37.90 (38.00)

- i. Infrared spectrophotometer: The spectra were recorded using SHIMADZU FTIR spectrophotometer, Central lab, Faculty of Science, Alexandria University.
- ii. UV-vis spectrophotometer and molar magnetic susceptibilities
The nujol mull electronic absorption spectra of complexes were recorded using Halios α instrument. Molar magnetic susceptibilities, corrected for diamagnetism using Pascal's constants, were determined at room temperature (298°K) using Faraday's method. The apparatus was calibrated with Hg[Co(SCN)₄].
- iii. Thermal analysis
The samples were measured using (DSC-60A detector, aluminum cell, nitrogen atmosphere and 50 ml/min flow rate).
- iv. Dielectric and electrical conductivity measurements
 - 1- Four test parameters including impedance $|Z|$, phase angle θ , parallel equivalent static capacitance C_p and loss tangent $\tan \delta$ were measured for complexes in the solid state at constant voltage 0.80 volt but different temperatures (40-240°C) and at variable frequencies (500 Hz - 5 MHz) using HIOKI "3532-50 LCR HITESTER" instrument.
 - 2- The complexes were prepared in the form of tablets at a pressure of 6-7 tons/cm² with 10 mm diameter and 1.48 mm thickness. Silver metal was evaporized on the major faces of each test piece to improve the contact with the measuring electrodes. The tablets were hold between two copper electrodes and then inserted with the holder vertically into cylindrical electric furnace. The potential drop across the heater was varied gradually through variable transformer to produce slow rate of increasing the temperature to get accurate temperature measurements using a pre-calibrated Cu-constantan thermocouple attached to the sample.

3- The dielectric constant ϵ , the dielectric loss ϵ'' , real part of impedance Z' , imaginary part Z'' , the conductivities $\sigma_{a.c.}$ (a.c.: alternating current condition), the relaxation times τ_0 , τ and the activation energies ΔE of the complexes were calculated.

v. Molecular Modeling

The ChemOffice Ultra 2004 computer and HyberChem programs are used for molecular modeling studies of the ligands and their complexes.

Results and Discussion

Mode of bonding of barbituric acid (BA) and its Th complex

The data are given in Table (2):

Table 2: Fundamental infrared band (cm^{-1}) of barbituric acid, uracil and their Th complex. (sp: splitted)

Barbituric acid (BA)	Th(BA) ₂	Uracil	Th-U	Assignments
3552	3360(sh)			
3478	-	3410	3418	ν_{OH}
3182	3177	3111	3101	
{3096}sp	{3123}sp	3041	3042	ν_{NH}
-	3003			
2876	2926	-	-	ν_{CH}
2830	2827			
1744	1710	1740	1724	
{1718}sp	-	1714	-	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$
1617	1634	1666	-	
-	1603	1643	1643	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$
1526	-	1522	1512	$\nu_{\text{C=C}}$
1410	1464	1460	1454	δ_{NH}
1366	1385	1420	1412	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}, \delta_{\text{CH}}$
1349	1346	1389	-	
1285	1288	-	-	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}, \delta_{\text{OH}}$
1232	1209	1244	1231	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$
1193	-			
-	1084			$\nu_{\text{C-O}}, \nu_{\text{C-N}}$
1028	1003	1000	997	$\nu_{\text{C-C}}$
936				
733	827	856	856	
739	777	822	-	
656	692	756	764	$\rho_{\text{CH}}, \rho_{\text{OH}}$
632	681			
-	538	-	546	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$
-	384	-	430	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$

- a- BA gave four IR bands [25] at 3552, 3478, 3182 and 3096 cm^{-1} due to ν_{OH} and ν_{NH} . The lower frequency of the ν_{NH} band compared to its normal position (3460-3400 cm^{-1}) points to the presence of an intramolecular hydrogen bonds of the type OH...N [26].
- b- Shifts of the ν_{OH} band of the free ligand occurred upon complexation, Table (2), due to the existence of coordinated water molecules or M-O and hydrogen bond formations [27].
- c- The band at 2876 cm^{-1} in the free ligand is due to ν_{CH} .

- d- The shifts or disappearance of both the ν_{NH} and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ bands, Table (2), suggest that these groups are strongly involved in the structural chemistry of the complexes. This is supported either by the probable existence of M-N bands or the free ligand may be subjected to half keto-half enol tautomerism and equilibria in the solid state [15], i.e. conversion of -CNH to C=N occurred.

Structure (IV) represents BA as 2,4,6-trihydroxypyrimidine. X-ray analysis indicated that structure (I) is the predominant form in the solid state [15].

- e- New IR bands of the complex appeared at (503-536 cm^{-1}) and (343-417 cm^{-1}) assigned as $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$, respectively. The ν_{OH} , $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ bands of BA are shifted on complexation, indicating M-O interaction.
- f- BA is of bidentate or tridentate bonding. The bidentate chelation is suggested to be through N(1) and C(2)O while the tridentate interaction is via C(2)O, N(3) and C(4)O.

For Th(BA)₂ complex, barbituric acid is tautomerized to give tridentate centers for coordination [3] and the presence of (ν_{OH} at 3360 cm^{-1} , ν_{NH} band at 3177-3123 cm^{-1}) upon complexation of Th(BA)₂, give a probability of association through hydrogen bonding. The following geometry is proposed:

Studies on uracil (U) and its Th complex, Table (2).

The bands at 3410 cm^{-1} and 3418 cm^{-1} in uracil and its Th complex, respectively, are due to ν_{OH} of type N-H...O [12,13].

The uracil ν_{NH} band at 3111 cm^{-1} is strongly affected on complexation with Th by shifting to lower wave number 3101 cm^{-1} which gives indication for Th-N interaction [10,14].

Both $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ bands of uracil at 1740 and 1714 cm^{-1} are affected on complexation to Th with different degrees. The first band is at 1724 cm^{-1} and the second band is absent, to assign the presence of Th-O interaction [13].

The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ bands of uracil at 1666 and 1643 cm^{-1} are assigned and compared upon complexation. The first band is absent while the second band isn't affected. Thus, uracil acts as a tridentate ligand through oxygen and nitrogen atoms on reaction with Th [11,14].

From data collected in Table(2) for Th(U)₂ complex, the presence of ν_{OH} , ν_{NH} and $\nu_{C=O}$ bands at 3418 cm⁻¹, 3101-3042 cm⁻¹ and 1724 cm⁻¹, respectively, upon complexation give a probability of association through hydrogen bonding.

The Th(BA)₂ complex gave electronic spectral bands at 311, 325 nm with $\mu_{eff} = 3.32$ B.M, assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ and d-d electronic transitions and typified the existence of octahedral high spin states [17].

Thermal analysis

The thermal behavior of Th(BA)₂ complex has been studied applying differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) [28-31], Figure (1),Table (3).

Table 3: DSC data and thermodynamic parameters of Th(BA)₂ complex

Compound	Heat range °C	T _m °C	ΔH J/g	ΔS J/g.°C	a	b	α	γ
Th(BA) ₂	264.96 – 321.27	301.93	-47.07	-0.156	-0.077	15.919	-2×10^{-8}	-0.036
	323.62 – 424.85	397.48	-100.75	-0.253	-0.467	211.375	-5×10^{-7}	0.083
					-0.818	411.120	-1×10^{-6}	-0.279
					1.134	-718.675	2×10^{-6}	-0.861
					-0.897	512.346	-8×10^{-7}	0.243
					0.800	-634.178	1×10^{-6}	-0.574
					0.139	-170.955	2×10^{-8}	-0.111
				-0.633	393.655	-4×10^{-7}	0.114	

Figure 1: DSC for Th(BA)₂

The Debye model [32] is used to describe capacity change over a large temperature range and C_p can be represented by the following empirical form: $C_p = aT + b$.

By plotting C_p versus T , a straight line is obtained, where a and b are parameters which can be determined from the slope and intercept of the line, respectively, Figure (2), Table (3).

The applications based on Debye model for selected complexes are given from the following equations [33]:

$$C_p \approx C_v = \alpha T^3 + \gamma T, \quad \frac{C_p}{T} = \alpha T^2 + \gamma$$

where α and γ are the coefficients of the lattice and electronic heat capacities, respectively. C_v is the heat capacity at constant volume which is assumed to be equal to C_p .

The relationships of $\frac{C_p}{T}$ versus T^2 gives straight line with slope α and intercept γ , Figure (3), Table (3). The straight lines are analyzed and the validity is calculated with R^2 values for each line, Figures(2, 3).

Figure 3: $\frac{C_p}{T} - T^2$ relationship for $Th(BA)_2$

The change in enthalpy (ΔH) for any phase transformation [34] taking place at any peak temperature, T_m , can be given by the following equation:

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H}{T_m} \quad (\text{at equilibrium, } \Delta G = 0)$$

The values of T_m (the peak temperature at which the peak is maximum or minimum), ΔH , ΔS , (a, b) parameters of Debye model, α and γ are given in Table (3).

The $Th(BA)_2$ complex gave exothermic peaks. All the change of entropy values, ΔS have $-ve$ signs where the activated transition states are more ordered, i.e. in a less random molecular configuration than that the reacting complexes [28,31].

Dielectric measurements

The dielectric parameters for the investigated complex are illustrated in terms of temperature and frequency ($\ln f$) changes, Figure (4). The more spotlight points, could be given as follows:

- 1- For a parallel-plate condenser in which a dielectric tablet fills the space between the plates, the capacitance is given by⁽³⁵⁾: $C_p = A\epsilon\epsilon_0 / d$

Where ϵ_0 is the permittivity of a vacuum and its value is approximately $8.854 \times 10^{-12} \text{ F m}^{-1}$, ϵ is the dielectric constant of a dielectric, a and d are the area and the thickness of the matter tablet, respectively. The capacitance (C_p) decreases with increasing the applied frequency in some different ranges which may be attributed to the effect of charge redistribution by carrier hopping on defects [36]. At low frequency, the charge on defects can be rapidly redistributed so that defects closer to the positive side of the applied field become negatively charged, while defects closer to the negative side of the applied field become positively charged. This leads to screening of the field and an overall reduction in the electric field. Because capacitance is inversely proportional to the field, this reduction in the field for a given voltage results in the increased capacitance observed as the frequency is lowered. In case of high frequency, the defects no longer have enough time to rearrange in response to the applied voltage, hence the capacitance decreases.

- 2- The complex dielectric permittivity, $\epsilon^*(\omega)$ is given as follows [37]: $\epsilon^*(\omega) = \epsilon'(\omega) - i\epsilon''(\omega)$ where $\epsilon'(\omega)$ and $\epsilon''(\omega)$ are the real and imaginary parts of the complex permittivity, respectively. ω is the angular frequency, $\omega = 2\pi f$ and $i = \sqrt{-1}$.

$$\epsilon'(\omega) = \epsilon \sin \theta, \quad \epsilon''(\omega) = \epsilon \cos \theta \quad \text{where } \theta \text{ is the phase shift.}$$

ϵ' and ϵ'' decrease with increasing frequency ($\ln f$), which can be explained as follows:

- (a) At low frequencies the dielectric constant for polar materials is due to the contribution of multi-component of polarizability, deformational polarization (electronic and ionic polarization) and relaxation polarization (orientational and interfacial polarization) [38].

- (b) When the frequency begins to increase, the dipoles will no longer be able to rotate sufficiently rapidly, so that their oscillations begin to lag behind those of the field. As the frequency is further increased, the dipole will be completely unable to follow the field and the orientation polarization stopped, so ϵ' and ϵ'' decrease at higher frequencies approaching a constant value due to the interfacial or space charge polarization only [39].
- The relative permittivity and dielectric loss values for the complexes, Figure (4), reveal semiconducting features based mainly on the hopping mechanism [40].
 - The loss tangent, $\tan \delta = \epsilon''/\epsilon'$, $\delta = 90^\circ - \theta$ which is decreased with increasing frequency.
 - The real and imaginary parts of the complex impedance are given by: $Z' = Z \cos \theta$, $Z'' = Z \sin \theta$ where Z' and Z'' are the real and imaginary parts of the impedance, respectively.

Figure 4: The dielectric parameters (Z , C_p , $|\theta|$, ϵ , ϵ' , ϵ'' , $\tan \delta$) - $\ln f$ relationships for $\text{Th}(\text{U})_2$ at different temperatures \diamond 40°C, \blacksquare 60°C, \blacktriangle 80°C, \times 100°C, \ast 120°C, \bullet 140°C, $+$ 160°C, $-$ 180°C, $-$ 200°C, \blacklozenge 220°C and \blacksquare 240°C

The impedance (Z) is mostly decreased with increasing frequency, Figure (4). The Z'' - Z' relationships are illustrated in Figure (5) at different temperatures. Dispersion arising during the transition from full orientational polarization at zero or low frequencies to negligible orientational polarization at high radio frequencies is referred to as dielectric relaxation [41]. The rate of decay and build-up of the orientational polarization, as given by the relaxation time τ , will depend upon the thermal energy of the dipoles as well as upon the internal or molecular friction forces encountered by the rotating dipoles.

Figure 5: Z'' - Z' relationship for complexes at different temperatures \blacklozenge 40°C, \blacksquare 60°C, \blacktriangle 80°C, \times 100°C, \times 120°C, \bullet 140°C, $+$ 160°C, \blacksquare 180°C, $-$ 200°C, \blacklozenge 220°C and \blacksquare 240°C

The most used of these methods consists by plotting the imaginary part $\varepsilon''(\omega)$ for a certain frequency against the real part $\varepsilon'(\omega)$ at the same frequency [42]. This diagram may be called the complex locus diagram or Argand diagram and was applied to dielectrics by Cole and Cole [43].

Cole and Cole generalized the representation of a Debye dielectric by a circular arc plot in the complex plane so that it is applied to a certain type of distributions of relaxation times, so

$$v/u = (\omega\tau_0)^{1-\alpha}$$

where ω is the angular frequency. The parameter α equals zero when the compound has only one relaxation time, whereas for a series of relaxation times, the value of α varies between 0 and 1. The extent of the distribution of relaxation times increases with increasing parameter α . On the other hand, the value of τ_0 decreases with increasing temperature. The molecular relaxation time τ could be determined based on the following equation [43]:

$$\tau = \frac{2\varepsilon_s + \varepsilon_\infty}{3\varepsilon_s} \tau_0$$

The relaxation time is interpreted as the average time which a molecule spends in one of the equilibrium positions before jumping to the other one. The temperature dependence of τ can be expressed for thermally activated processes as [38]:

$$\tau = \tau_0 e^{E_0/kT}$$

where τ_0 is a constant characteristic relaxation time and represents the time of a single oscillation of a dipole in a potential well, E_0 is the energy of activation for the relaxation of the dipole, k is the Boltzmann constant and τ represents the average or most probable value of the spread of the relaxation times. The Cole-Cole diagrams for $\text{Th}(\text{U})_2$ complex at different temperatures, Figures (6), Table (4) reveal mainly non-Debye type.

The variation of $\ln\tau$ as a function of reciprocal absolute temperature for ligands and complexes, Figure (7), assigned that as the temperature increases, the relaxation time for each relaxator becomes smaller. The activation energy for the relaxation process of $\text{Th}(\text{BA})_2$ complex is 6.16kJ mol^{-1} .

Figure 7: $\ln \tau$ - $1000/T$ relationship for $\text{Th}(\text{U})_2$ complexTable 4: The dielectric data obtained from the analysis of Cole-Cole diagrams for $\text{Th}(\text{U})_2$ complex

Compound	Temperature (K)	ω	V	u	α	$\frac{\pi}{2}$	α	$1 - \alpha$	$\tau_0 \times 10^{-8}$	ϵ_s	ϵ_∞	$\tau \times 10^{-8}$	$\ln \tau$
$\text{Th}(\text{U})_2$	313	21362830.0	0.90	1.15	45	0.5000	0.5000	2.86702	13.41	4.55	2.23560	-17.6162	
	333		1.00	1.80	45	0.5000	0.5000	1.44476	13.64	1.82	1.02743	-18.3936	
	353		1.05	1.75	23	0.2556	0.7444	2.35687	12.73	1.82	1.68357	-17.8998	
	373		0.90	1.60	22	0.2444	0.7556	2.18585	11.59	1.82	1.57165	-17.9686	
	393		0.80	1.70	30	0.3333	0.6667	1.51113	10.34	2.07	1.10826	-18.3179	
	413		0.80	1.75	32	0.3556	0.6444	1.38943	10.00	2.07	1.02215	-18.3988	
	433		0.80	1.70	32	0.3556	0.6444	1.45335	10.00	2.07	1.06918	-18.3538	
	453		0.80	1.70	32	0.3556	0.6444	1.45335	10.00	2.07	1.06918	-18.3538	
	473		0.80	1.70	31	0.3444	0.6556	1.48245	10.00	1.90	1.08219	-18.3417	
	493		0.80	1.70	31.5	0.3500	0.6500	1.46795	9.82	1.90	1.07331	-18.3499	
513	0.80	1.70	32	0.3556	0.6444	1.45335	9.66	1.90	1.06419	-18.3585			

τ Ranges for $\text{Th}(\text{U})_2$ is $(1.22353 \times 10^{-8} - 5.25957 \times 10^{-6})$.

Electrical conductivity measurements

The alternating current conductivity (σ) is calculated according to the following equation:

$$\sigma (\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}) = \omega \times C_p (\text{pF}) \times \tan \delta \times \frac{d}{A} (\text{cm}^{-1}) \times 10^{-12}$$

The frequency dependence of a. c. conductivity for $\text{Th}(\text{U})_2$ complex at different temperatures, Figure (8), where the a. c. conductivity gradually increases with increasing the frequency. At lower frequencies the grain boundaries are more effective than grains in electrical conduction hence the hopping of ions are bound at lower frequencies. As the frequency of the applied field increases the conductive grains become more active and promote the conduction mechanism [44].

Figure 8: A. C. conductivity σ - $\ln f$ relationship for $\text{Th}(\text{U})_2$ complexes at different temperatures $\blacklozenge 40^\circ\text{C}$, $\blacksquare 60^\circ\text{C}$, $\blacktriangle 80^\circ\text{C}$, $\times 100^\circ\text{C}$, $\times 120^\circ\text{C}$, $\bullet 140^\circ\text{C}$, $+ 160^\circ\text{C}$, $\blacksquare 180^\circ\text{C}$, $- 200^\circ\text{C}$, $\blacklozenge 220^\circ\text{C}$ and $\blacksquare 240^\circ\text{C}$

The conductivities have a magnitude close to that of semiconductors [45], where the electrons in the orbitals are not of sufficient mobility to be promoted.

The investigation of electron transport in disorder systems has been gradually developed, while for gap states is of particular interest, because of their effect on the electrical properties of semiconductor materials. Several concepts proposed by many workers start from the premise that the contribution of carriers hopping between localized states to electrical conductivity is expected in amorphous semiconductors. The hopping conduction can be easily distinguished from that of the band conduction by measuring the frequency dependence of conductivity, which as expected, is due to conduction in localized states.

The electrical conduction mechanism of solids is based on [46,47]:

- 1- The conductivity depends on the mobility of π -electrons.
- 2- In the molecule, the π -electrons are localized in the molecule framework and their delocalization requires activation energy.
- 3- The delocalized π -electrons migrate to the neighboring molecule by tunnel effect. As the temperature increases, the bonds are exhausted resulting in an increase of the conductivity.

The electrical conductivity of substances at a given frequency varies exponentially with the absolute temperature according to the Arrhenius relation:

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 e^{-\Delta E/kT}$$

where σ is the electrical conductivity at an absolute temperature T , σ_0 is the pre-exponential factor, ΔE is the activation energy.

The activation energy data and $\ln \sigma_0$ values for ligands and complexes are given in Figure (9) and Table (5).

Table 5: The activation energy data $\Delta E(\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$ and $\ln \sigma_0$ values for $\text{Th}(\text{U})_2$ complex at different frequencies

Compound	Frequency (kHz)	$\ln \sigma_0$	$\Delta E (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$
$\text{Th}(\text{U})_2$	10	-14.15	20.08
	50	-12.41	23.11
	100	-10.07	31.91
	500	-11.05	24.26
	1000	-9.90	29.56

Figure 9: $\ln \sigma - 1000/T$ relationship for $\text{Th}(\text{U})_2$ complex at different frequencies \blacklozenge 10kHz, \blacksquare 50 kHz, \blacktriangle 100 kHz, \times 500 kHz and \times 1000 kHz

Figure 10: The molecular modeling of Barbituric acid (BA), a) ChemOffice, b) HyperChem

The relationship between molecular structure and electrical properties was deduced, where two pathways for the conduction of electricity may be expected. The first conducting process occurring in the lower temperature region is attributed to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions which require less energy to be performed. In the upper temperature region, conduction could be attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions which need more energy to participate in electronic conduction. The observed increment of conduction in the upper temperature region may be attributed to interactions between $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The lower temperature range is the region of extrinsic semiconductor where the conduction is due to the excitation of carriers from donor localized level to the conduction band. In the upper temperature range, the intrinsic region is reached where carriers are thermally activated from the valence band to the conduction band. This behavior can be explained as follows: the upper temperature range may be attributed to the interaction between the electrons of d-orbitals and the p-orbitals of the ligand. This interaction will lead to small delocalization of the p-electronic charge on the ligand which tends to increase the activation energy. The presence of d-electrons in a narrow energy band leads to magnetic ordering and degeneracy of d-bands with respect to the orbital quantum number, which is only partially lifted in a crystal field [48].

For $\text{Th}(\text{U})_2$ complex during thermal agitation, an additional increase in electrical conductivity occurs, which probably indicating a discontinuity of the chemical bonds existing in the structure.

Th forms a bridge with the ligands, thus facilitating the transfer of current carriers with some degree of delocalization in the excited state during measurements. Meanwhile, this leads to an increase of the electrical conductivity with a decrease in energy of activation [48].

Molecular Modeling

The molecular modeling calculations of the compounds, Figure (10) are given concerning the bond lengths, bond angles, dihedral angles and HyperChem data, Table (6b). These calculations are based on using molecular orbital package (MOPAC) for minimizing energies where the Austin Model 1 (AM1) method is used, also Parameterized Model 3 (PM3) is applied for HyperChem.

Different parameters (heat of formation, gradient norm, dipole, charges, solvation in water, electrostatic potential, molecular surfaces, spin density, hyperfine coupling constants and polarizabilities) are of major importance to control the modeling of the compounds.

Table 6a: Quantum chemical parameters (eV) of compounds calculated by PM3 method

Compound	E_{HOMO}	E_{LUMO}	$\Delta E = (E_{\text{L}} - E_{\text{H}})$	χ	μ	η	σ	ω
BA	-10.828	-0.421	10.407	5.6245	-5.6245	5.2035	0.1922	3.0398
U	-9.710	-0.511	9.199	5.1105	-5.1105	4.5995	0.2174	2.8391

Table (6b): HyperChem calculations of compounds calculated by PM3 method

HyperChem calculations	(kcal/mol) (BA)	(kcal/mol) (U)
Total energy	-40174.049	-33385.590
Binding energy	-1420.823	-1304.879
Isolated atomic energy	-38753.226	-32080.711
Electronic energy	-165585.243	-132951.621
Core-core interaction	125411.193	99566.030
Heat of formation	-124.178	-67.794
Dipole moment	0.810 Debye.	3.990 Debye.
Net charges of atoms	(1(-0.024), 2 (0.230), 3(-0.361), 4(-0.024), 5(0.251), 6(-0.334), 7(-0.145), 8(0.251), 9(-0.334), 10(0.127), 11(0.127), 12 (0.117) and 13(0.118)).	(1(-0.011), 2 (0.208), 3(-0.387), 4(0.089), 5(-0.065), 6(-0.277), 7(0.298), 8(-0.352), 9(0.121), 10(0.105), 11(0.124) and 12(0.145)).

Quantum chemical parameters such as the highest occupied molecular orbital energy (E_{HOMO}) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital energy (E_{LUMO}) were given using HyperChem modeling, where energy gap (ΔE) and parameters which give information about the reactive chemical behavior of compounds such as electronegativity (χ), chemical potential (μ), global hardness (η), softness (σ) and electrophilicity index (ω) were calculated, Table (6a).

$$\Delta E = E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}}$$

The concepts of these parameters are related to each other, the energies of the (HOMO) and (LUMO) orbitals of the molecule are related to ionization potential (I) and the electron affinity (A), respectively, and their relations with χ and μ are given by the following equations:

$$I = -E_{\text{HOMO}} \quad \mu = -\chi$$

$$A = -E_{\text{LUMO}} \quad \mu = \frac{-(I+A)}{2} = \frac{E_{\text{HOMO}} + E_{\text{LUMO}}}{2}$$

The qualitative definition of hardness is related to the polarizability, because a decrease of the energy gap usually leads to an easier polarization of the molecule.

$$\eta = \frac{I-A}{2} = \frac{E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}}}{2}$$

The inverse of the hardness is equal to softness, (σ) as follows:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\eta}$$

The energy difference between the HOMO and LUMO (HOMO-LUMO gap) can be used to predict the strength and stability of transition metal complexes. Hard molecules have a large HOMO-LUMO gap while, soft molecules have a small HOMO-LUMO gap. Soft molecules have small excitation energies to the excited states; therefore they will be more polarizable and more reactive than the hard molecules. Hard molecules resist changes in their electron number and distribution.

The electrophilicity index (ω) in terms of chemical potential (μ) and hardness (η) is given from the equation [49]:

$$\omega = \frac{\mu^2}{2\eta}$$

HOMO-LUMO gaps are mostly decreased and softness increased upon complexation with different ligands, also the total evolved energies are increased which give stabilization for complex formation.

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